

HOW TO DESIGN FAMILY GAMES FOR PRIMARY SCHOOL STUDENTS

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<https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7952240>

ARTICLE INFO

Received: 12th May 2023

Accepted: 19th May 2023

Online: 20th May 2023

KEY WORDS

Effective, video games, easy to learn, creativity, interactive, Intervention.

ABSTRACT

A growing trend in educational settings is the usage of instructional games. The literature has extensively examined the immersive and motivating aspects of game-based learning, but the systematic development and use of educational games is still a controversial subject. In this work, a generic game design approach that incorporates adaptability and evaluation aspects is provided after several pertinent needs for the creation of educational games in online education are studied. In view of its relevance to different implementations and situations, a specific implementation of that concept is presented in the final section.

INTRODUCTION

Due to time and logistical constraints, many instructors find it difficult to seamlessly integrate games into lectures, despite the fact that they view game-based learning (GBL) as a tool to engage students and cater to a variety of learning styles.

To include game-based learning into your classroom, follow these five steps:

1. Determine Game-Based Learning's Goals

Your search will be more focused and you'll be more likely to locate the right game if you decide how you'll utilize it.

Determine if you want to utilize a game for: before doing any study.

Intervention – If a student is having problems demonstrating that they grasp the fundamentals, you can think about utilizing a game to help them. Therefore, the game you select should offer material that adapts to user knowledge and learning preferences.

- Enrichment – You could desire a game that uses various media to provide content as pupils understand basic concepts. As an illustration, it may provide questions using text, audio, visuals, and more. As they experiment with novel methods to assimilate the material, this should inspire students to challenge themselves.

- Reinforcement – Classes as a whole can play games to reinforce curricular material rather than utilizing games to instruct and engage individual students. Due of this, game-based learning may also be done in groups. Students may naturally compete against one another to obtain greater scores in some games since they offer multiplayer elements.

Finding a game that satisfies the needs of both teachers and students will probably go more quickly if these considerations are kept in mind.

2. Play the game on your own, checking that it adheres to the learning objectives

You can decide if a game is in line with your learning objectives by actually playing it.

Play a game you believe is acceptable after finding it, and note:

- **Teacher Control** – A lot of educational games allow teachers to modify settings and material for specific pupils. For instance, some allow you to give questions to particular players while matching them to in-class material.
- **Intuitiveness** – A game, whether it be physical or digital, should be simple to operate. Instead of worrying about how the game functions, students can challenge themselves by thinking through and proving their understanding of the material.
- **Engagement** – Ascertain if kids will enjoy the game based on the content and the way it is delivered. Students should naturally desire to participate and learn if the activity is enjoyable.
- **material Types** – The game should include a variety of material to fit various learning methods. For instance, questions could be presented as graphs, numbers, and word problems in a math education video game.
- **information Levels**- The game should employ differentiated teaching techniques to tailor information to each player in order to cover a variety of problem areas and aptitudes. For instance, a language video game may instruct one student more on pronouns than another.

You should be able to determine if the game effectively supports learning objectives by paying attention to these factors while you play.

3. Make sure it satisfies parental expectations

Before choosing a game, you might want to get input from other instructors or administrators, but parents should be informed of your plans for using games to teach.

This opens the door to parent involvement, which is one of the most reliable indicators of students' achievement, according to often referenced studies from the National Committee for Citizens in Education:

From early infancy through high school, the family is crucial to students' academic success. There are enormous benefits when schools include parents and kids. Children do better in school and remain in school longer when parents are active at school as well as at home.

Additionally, you probably don't want children to tell their parents that they played games for an hour in class. They might not consider games that are instructive.

These worries could be allayed by writing home and outlining the advantages of the game and possibly include your email address. Prodigy provides the following letter to instructors who register for our math game.

Offering this kind of transparent information should facilitate adoption from both a teacher's and an administrative standpoint.

4. Commit Time to Regular In-Class Work Play

Inconsistent, organized playtime may be more beneficial for students' learning than sporadic game-based learning. Additionally, it might not be as captivating as it might be.

For instance, a research that appeared in the journal Educational Technology and Society established a link between an organized 40-minute session of educational game play

and enhanced problem-solving abilities in addition to faster recall processes. Make time for game-based learning activities in a classroom with 1:1 device use by:

- Including game time as a scheduled activity in your lesson plan, not as an afterthought

- Using a game as a way to get students interested in the lesson's subject
- Making use of a game as a way to let pupils leave and contemplate.

Make time for game-based learning activities in a classroom with minimal gadget use by:

- Paying greater attention to analog games, including instructional board games.
- Establishing learning stations, one of which involves playing a game on a gadget.
- Playing team games and allowing students to participate in groups or pairs.

These choices ought to make it simpler to set aside time for educational play and smoothly integrate game-based learning into the classroom.

5. Evaluate Play's Progress to Inform Instruction

Data gathered from the games you use can help you improve in-class education by revealing student strengths and weaknesses.

Depending on the goal and style of the game in question, several types of data will be collected.

It typically includes the following technique:

- In-Game Reports – Some educational video games include in-game instructor reports that track student success. Charts, for instance, will provide each player's scores for a set of questions and allow you to click for further information.
- Self-Reports – In video games without reporting features or physical games, you may encourage students to take responsibility for their own development by having them self-report. For each student, make a Google Forms spreadsheet. then request updates from them.
- Discussions in class -- Following team games, having a class-wide conversation enables each group to discuss challenges, advancements, and successes.

By completing this last level of game-based learning integration, you will have the knowledge necessary to modify courses and activities, correcting problem areas and expanding on newly acquired knowledge.

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